

Sex differences in the efficacy and tolerability of antipsychotics in people with an acute exacerbation of schizophrenia: protocol for an individual-participant-data, dose-response, network meta-analysis

SAGER checklist

SAGER item		Manuscript section and comment
General principles		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authors should use the terms <i>sex</i> and <i>gender</i> carefully in order to avoid confusing both terms. 		We used the terms carefully throughout the manuscript, referring to sex as a biological construct and gender as a sociocultural construct.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where the subjects of research comprise organisms capable of differentiation by sex, the research should be designed and conducted in a way that can reveal sex-related differences in the results, even if these were not initially expected. 		The examination of subgroup differences based on sex is main aim of this project. As noted in Table 1, we will accept any definition and method of collecting information on sex used in the included trials of the meta-analysis, as variability is expected (e.g., self-report, sex assigned at birth).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where subjects can also be differentiated by gender (shaped by social and cultural circumstances), the research should be conducted similarly at this additional level of distinction. 		The examination of subgroup differences based on gender is beyond the main aims of this project. Moreover, as noted in the introduction, Table 1, and limitations, most trials included in the meta-analysis were likely conducted before distinctions between sex and gender were widely recognized or systematically captured in clinical research. Therefore, a more detailed analysis at this level is not feasible.
Recommendations per section of the article		
Title and abstract	If only one sex is included in the study, or if the results of the study are to be applied to only one sex or gender, the title and the abstract should specify the sex of animals or any cells, tissues and other material derived from these and the sex and gender of human participants.	This is not applicable to our study, which focuses on the examination of subgroup differences based on sex.
Introduction	Authors should report, where relevant, whether sex and/or gender differences may be expected.	The potential importance and expectation of sex and gender differences is addressed in the introduction.
Methods	Authors should report how sex and gender were taken into account in the design of the study, whether they ensured adequate representation of males and females, and justify the reasons for any exclusion of males or females.	There are no restrictions in the eligibility criteria of participants in terms of sex or gender (see "Eligibility criteria"). The definition of the variables sex and gender is described in more detail in Table 1. The analysis outlined in "Data Synthesis" focuses on examining sex differences in the effects of antipsychotic drugs.
Results	Where appropriate, data should be routinely presented disaggregated by sex and gender. Sex- and gender-based analyses should be reported regardless of positive or negative outcome. In clinical trials, data on withdrawals and dropouts should also be reported disaggregated by sex.	As noted in "Data Synthesis", we will report sex-disaggregated summary data and, if feasible, conduct sex-based analyses. Disaggregation of data based on gender, or gender-based analyses, is beyond the main aim of the project and is unlikely to be possible due to limited data availability (see Table 1).
Discussion	The potential implications of sex and gender on the study results and analyses should be discussed. If	The potential implications of the results of this protocol, as well as the limitations

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	a sex and gender analysis was not conducted, the rationale should be given. Authors should further discuss the implications of the lack of such analysis on the interpretation of the results.	related to the definitions of sex and gender in the included studies of the meta-analysis, are addressed in the "Discussion".
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